

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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MUNDARIJA

Ilm-fanga baxshida umr	10
Baxtiyor Islamov	
Kichik biznesni rivojlantirishda “yashil” iqtisodiyotni keng tatbiq qilishning ahamiyati	12
Gulnora Abdurahmonova Kalandarovna, Sanjar Baxodirovich G’oipnazarov	
Brand Capital as a Determinant of Institutional Prestige and Student Choice in the Higher Education System	18
Zufarova Nozima Gulamiddinovna	
Inson va atrof-muhit dialektikasi: nomutanosiblik ko’rsatkichlari va ekologik muammolar	26
Butaboyev Maxammadjon Tuychiyevich, Maxmudov Nosir Maxmudovich	
Yashil budjetlashtirish va uni O’zbekistonda joriy etish istiqbollari	32
Meyliev Obid Raxmatullayevich, Gofurova Kamola Xayrulla qizi	
Iqtisodiyotda ta’lim va fan integratsiyasining asosiy yo’nalishlari	37
Yormatov Ilmidin Toshmatovich	
Transport vositalari va yo’llar turizm transport infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishning muhim omilidir	41
Agzamov Shaxboz Akmalovich	
Bank xizmatlarini raqamlashtirish orqali samaradorligini oshirish	46
A. X. Salamov	
Biznes-reja baliqchilik xo’jaligi rivojlanishi uchun asos sifatida	50
Dosmurotova Shaxista Kengashovna	
Mamlakatning investitsiyaviy jozibadorligi va uning lizing munosabatlari rivojlanishi bilan bog’liqligi	57
Axmediyeva Aliya Toxtarovna	
Turizmni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari	65
Ziyadullayev Ilhom Narkabilovich	
Tijorat banklari depozit operatsiyalari samaradorligini oshirish muammolari va ularni bartaraf etish yo’llari	69
Shamsiyev Nodir Muratovich	
Hududlarni rivojlantirishda xorijiy investitsiyalarning samaradorligini oshirish masalalari	74
Shagzatov Oybek bahodirovich	
Hududlar biznes muhitini rivojlantirish va samarali boshqarish yo’nalishlari	78
Davlatov Sanjar Abdimannonovich	
Ijtimoiy rivojlanish xulq-atvor paradigmasida yoshlarning tadbirkorlik faoliyatini tartibga solishning nazariy asoslari	82
Mirzatov Baxtiyor Toxirovich	
Korxonalar innovatsion faoliyatida raqamli transformatsiyaning muhim yo’nalishlari	86
Yuldasheva Kamola Miraliyevna	
O’zbekistonda agroturizmni rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish (Buxoro viloyati misolida)	91
Yoriyeva Farangiz Murodillayevna	
Innovatsion tadbirkorlik muhitini kompleks baholashda xalqaro tashkilotlar tajribasi	96
Nazarova Umida Avazovna	
Turizm faoliyatini davlat tomonidan tartibga solish samaradorligini oshirishning ayrim usullari	100
Mirzaxodjayev Alisher Botirovich	
Globalashuv sharoitida transchegaraviy suv resurslardan samarali foydalanishni boshqirish	105
Mirzayev Musurmon Umidullayevich	

Surxondaro viloyati iqtisodiyotida kichik biznes va tadbirkorlikning o'рни va ahamiyati.....	110
Fayziyeva Aziza Azamat qizi	
Ta'lim muassasalarida xarajatlarni moliyaviy nazorat etishning samaradorligi tahlili.....	115
Eshonqulov Davlatjon Rajaboyevich	
Ta'minot zanjirini boshqarishda transport logistikasi usullarini takomillashtirish.....	121
Zoxidova Nazokat Berdimurot qizi	
Blokcheyn texnologiyasida xavfsizlik masalalari	125
Mamadiyarov Zokir Toshtemirovich	
Развитие цифровой трансформации банковского сектора Республики Узбекистан.....	131
Абдурахманова Матлуба Махамдаминовна	
Asosiy fondlarni hisoblash va baholash usullarini takomillashtirish istiqbollari.....	137
Rixsimbayev Odiljon Qobiljonovich	
Marketingda tovar harakati tizimini optimallashtirish va modellashtirish	143
Sherzod Xolmurodovich Pardayev, Kamola Abdujabborovna Pardayeva	
Iqtisodiy rivojlanish uchun strategik taqsimlash strategiyalari: Investitsion Fond Portfellarning qiyosiy tahlili.....	150
Sultonboeva Munira bahodirovna	
Soliq munosabatlarining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati: ilmiy-nazariy qarashlar.....	156
Axrоров Zarif Oripovich, Saidmurodov Feruz Sodiqjon o'g'li	
Взаимосвязь инвестиционной стратегии с оценкой эффективности инвестиционного проекта	161
С. С. Алиева, А. Назаров	
Erkin iqtisodiy zonalarning faoliyati va boshqaruv mexanizmini takomillashtirish.....	169
Sheraliyeva Saida Azatovna	
Xizmat safari xarajatlari hisobining huquqiy asoslari	172
Ergashev Sarvar Xudoynazarovich	
Инклюзивное образование и его особенности.....	177
Зайнутдинова Умида Джалоловна	
Jismoniy shaxslarning mol-mulk va yer soliqlarini hisoblash va undirish samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	181
Qurbonov Muxiddin Abdullayevich	
Mamlakatda soliq qarzdorligi vujudga kelishining asosiy sabablari va ularni qisqartirish yo'llari.....	186
Hakimov Ulug'bek Furqat o'g'li	
Mulk qiymatini baholash tushunchasi, baholash obyektlari, baholanadigan qiymat turlari.....	190
Izbosarov Boburjon Bahriddinovich, Yoqubboyev Ilhomjon G'ulomjon o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda sug'urta xizmatlarining zamonaviy transformatsiyasi.....	195
G. Adilova	
Biznes subyektlarida samaradorlik masalalarini o'yinlar nazariyasi usuli bilan baholash.....	199
Mardiyev Nurali	
Yengil sanoatda "lean production" konsepsiyasini tatbiq etishning amaliy jihatlar.....	205
Yaxyayeva Inobat Karimovna	
Soliq salohiyatini baholash usullari va ularning tadbirkorlik subyektlari faoliyatiga ta'siri tahlili	209
Borotov Sharofiddin Jumaqul o'g'li	
Ko'chmas mulk bozorini baholashning institutsional asoslari	215
Ishonqulov Nizamjon Fayzullayevich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida turizm xizmatlarini rivojlantirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari.....	223
Amriyeva Shaxzoda Shuxratovna	
O'zbekistonning bank-moliya tizimi hamda unda Islom moliyasi instrumentlarini jalb etishdagi joriy tendensiyalar	228
Eshimov Alisher Dasmurodovich	

Tashqi savdoda notarif usullarni qo'llashning iqtisodiy oqibatlarini aniqlash metodologiyasi (rivojlangan davlatlar tajribasi)	236
Norqobilov Akobir Iso o'g'li	
Reklama xizmatlari va uning subyektlar samaradorligini oshirishdagi imkoniyatlari.....	242
Rabbimov Elbek Abdulloyevich	
Ijtimoiy siyosatni amalga oshirishda sog'liqni saqlash tizimini moliyalashtirish asoslari	247
Imonqulov Nuriddin Qo'shmon o'g'li	
Tijorat banklari biznes ekotizimini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	252
Shoyardonov Orziqul Jo'ra o'g'li	
Majburiy tibbiy sug'urtaning vujudga kelishi va o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	258
Kenjayev Soxib Sayfiyevich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida zamonaviy soliq ma'murchiligini joriy etish orqali budjet-soliq siyosati samaradorligini yanada oshirish	262
Yuldasheva Shaxnoza Xojiakbar qizi	
Jahon iqtisodiyotining barqaror rivojlanishida derivativlar bozorining roli	268
Shokirov Mirkamol Mirolim o'g'li	
Boshqaruv hisobida mas'uliyat markazlarini tashkil etish masalalari	276
Sobirov Otabek Olimjonovich	
Davlat moliyasini boshqarishda moliyaviy nazorat usullaridan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	279
Kultayev Farxod Shavkatovich	
Tijorat banklari foydasi va rentabillik ko'rsatkichlariga ta'sir etuvchi omillar tahlilini takomillashtirish	283
Normo'minov Temurbek Sheraliyevich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida tijorat banklari aktivlar sifatini oshirish yo'llari	286
To'ychiyev Otabek Shamshiyevich	
Venchur kapitalining mohiyati va O'zbekistonda venchur tizimini rivojlantirishning institutsional asoslari.....	290
Tadjibayeva Nigora Gulomjonovna	
Innovatsiyalar: zamonaviy iqtisodiyot uchun innovatsion faoliyatni qo'llab-quvvatlash zarurati.....	295
Malikova Dilrabo Muminovna, Tursunov Jahongir Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Budjet daromadlarining shakllanishida egri soliqlarning ta'sirini ko'p omilli ekonometrik modellashtirishda tahlil qilish.....	299
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norqo'chqor qizi	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarida investitsion jozibadorlikni oshirish yo'llari	304
Abdullayev Boburjon Akbaraliyevich	
Barcha tadbirkorlik subyektlariga teng raqobat sharoitini yaratishda soliq imtiyozlarining o'rni	308
Akbarov Akmalxon Akrom o'g'li	
Hisob siyosati va unda biologik aktivlar hisobini yoritib berish tartibini takomillashtirish	312
Mirzayeva Nargiza Batirovna	
Talabalarning oilali bo'lishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillarga iqtisodiy baholashda yangicha yondashuv.....	316
O. U. Shomurodov, A. A. Suyarov, Z. U. Uroqov, J. S. Urazov, A. T. Ablahatov	
Ways to Use the Experience of Foreign Countries in Creating a Beneficial Business Environment for Entrepreneurship And Improving Taxation	321
Mukhlisa Ikramova	
Aholi turmush darajasini oshirishda moliyaviy savodxonlikning o'rni va iqtisodiy rivojlanishga ta'siri	327
Yusupov Muhammadali Soxib o'g'li, J.D. Xojiyev	
Temir yo'l sanoat korxonalarida ijtimoiy-mehnat munosabatlarini boshqarish bo'yicha xorijiy tajriba.....	331
Kadirova Sharofat Amonovna	
Механизм внедрения аутсорсинговой деятельности в АО “Ўзтемирўйўйловчи”	334
Н. Э. Кахарова	

Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni yanada rivojlantirish investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi	339
Sharipov Bobur Anvar o'g'li	
"STEKLOPLASTIK" MJCHning bozordagi strategik holatini tahlil qilish	344
Musyeva Shoira Azimovna	
Agrar sektorda ekologik toza mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarishning nazariy masalalari	350
M. Sh. Nazarova, Z. S. Kazakova	
Methodological Foundations of Bank Lending and Classification of Factors Affecting the Features of Obtaining Loans.....	355
Raxmanova Laylo bahodirovna, A. Karimova	
Agrosanoat klasterlarda tovar-moddiy zaxiralar samaradorligini KPI orqali baholash uslubiyati	359
Toshpo'latov Azizbek Shermuxamadovich	
Faol tadbirkorlar faoliyatida kambag'al oilalarni iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy holatini yaxshilash imkoniyatlari	364
Salamov Ibrohim, Nazarova Maryam Sharifovna, Kazakova Zulayxo Saloxiddinovna, Jonibekov Faxriddin Beknazarovich, Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich, Ulmasova Oygul Baxtiyorovna, Xamdamova Nasiba Ablakulovna, Xudayberdiyeva Ma'rifat Umarovna	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar strategiyasi tahlilining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	371
Tursunova Shaxnoza Farxod qizi	
Процессы цифровизации АО "Hududgazta'minot"	375
Хусанов Кахрамон Нишонович	
O'zbekistonda aholi turmush darajasini oshirish yo'llari.....	380
Abdullayeva Madina Kamilovna, Eldorbekov G'ofurbek Iskandarbek o'g'li	
Aholi farovonligini oshirishda tadbirkorlik subyektlari uchun kredit tizimini takomillashtirish mexanizmi	383
Bobayev Isroiljon Abdinabiyevich	
Mamlakatga jalb qilingan xorijiy kapitalning tovarlar va xizmatlar importi salohiyatiga ta'sirini ekonometrik modellar bilan baholash	388
Saydullayev Azamat Jo'raqul o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda bank xizmatlari raqobatbardoshligini baholash mazmuni va o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	396
Sh. Madraimov	
Kapital bozorida sug'urta kompaniyalar institutsional investor sifatida	399
Xasanova Lola Mamasharifovna	
Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasida institutsional islohotlarni yanada chuqurlashtirish va ko'p funksiyali raqamlashtirishning ilmiy asoslari	402
B. B. Berkinov	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi tijorat banklari orqali jinoiy yo'l bilan olingan daromadlarni legallashtirish mexanizmlari	411
G'afurov Umidjon Bahodir o'g'li	
Rivojlangan mamlakatlarda keksa fuqarolarning bandligini oshirish kam ta'minlangan aholi qatlamini qo'llab-quvvatlash usuli sifatida (Yaponiya tajribasi misolida)	415
Karimov Bekzodjon Iloxomovich	
Tashqi savdoni oshirishda boj-tarif siyosatini takomillashtirish mexanizmlari	422
Pardayev Ilhomjon G'ulomjon o'g'li	
Финансы или корпоративные финансы.....	428
Уринов Бобур Насиллоевич	
In Ensuring Economic Development in the Country Green Economy and its Features	434
Akhunova Shakhistakhon Nomonjanovna, Abdusattorova Mokhirabonu Abdugoppor kizi	
Tijorat banklarining investitsiya faoliyatini rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	439
Jo'rayev O'ktam Panji o'g'li	

Сокращение уровня бедности в Узбекистане.....	445
Амирджанова Ситора Суннат кизи	
Paxtachilik sohasida ishlab chiqarish jarayonlari samaradorligini oshirishning innovatsion yechimlari va uning foydaga ta'sirini baholash.....	450
S. B. Inoyatov	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlar bilan ishlash amaliyotidagi muammolar va ularni barataraf etish yo'llari.....	455
Maxmudov Rahimjon Hamid o'g'li	
Mahalliy budjet daromadlarining nazariy va ilmiy asoslari.....	462
Ollokulova Feruza Mansurovna	
Kambag'allikni qisqartirish – aholi turmush farovonligini ta'minlashning muhim omili.....	465
Usmanov Baxodir Baxtiyorovich	
Raqamli marketingni rivojlantirish zaruriyati.....	471
Xalmuxamedova Zeboxon Babaxanovna	
Tijorat banklari o'rtasidagi raqobatni rivojlantirish orqali fond bozorida aksiyalar narxini barqarorligini ta'minlash istiqbollari.....	475
M. Yuldosheva	
Konchilik sanoati korxonalarida innovatsion faoliyatni rivojlantirish mexanizmlarining ilmiy-nazariy asoslari.....	482
Kurbanova Mehriniso Nematjanovna	
O'zbekistonda banklar moliyaviy xizmatlari va ular sifatining amaldagi holati tahlili.....	489
Mirzayev Mirza Abdullayevich	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarining iqtisodiy samaradorlikning raqobatbardoshligini instituttsional tahlil qilish mexanizmi.....	494
Saydullayeva Saodat Abdumajidovna	
Integrasiya sharoitida to'qimachilik sanoatining rivojlanishi.....	501
Ziyayeva Muhtasar Mansurdjanovna	
Auditorlik tekshiruvini tashkil etish va o'tkazish jarayonlarini takomillashtirish.....	505
Karamatova Noiba Husnitdinovna	
Davlatning iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlashning nazariy jihatlari.....	512
Mamatov Mamajan Axmadjonovich	
Экономическое сознание и экономическое мышление: теоретический анализ.....	519
Пардаев Мамаюнус Каршибаевич, Мухаммедов Мурод Мухаммедович	
O'zbekiston respublikasi tijorat banklari tomonidan qurilish korxonalarini kreditlashni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	524
Sultanov Vaxram Begdullayevich	
Роль искусственного интеллекта в современных технологиях медиаобразования в высших учебных заведениях.....	528
Самигова Гуландом Абдужаббаровна	
Talabalarga moliyaviy yordam dasturlari va ularning ta'lim sifatiga ta'siri.....	536
Mirzayeva Muhlisa Ubaydullo qizi	
Mintaqaviy investitsion jozibadorlik va investitsion siyosat: nazariy talqin.....	541
Muminov Akmal Tulkunovich	
Mamlakatni ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyotida oliy ta'lim tizimining ta'siri.....	545
Nasimov Adiz Azamat o'g'li, Baxtiyorova Jasmina Jasurovna, Axrorov Zarif Oripovich	
Respublikada fermer xo'jaliklarga xizmat ko'rsatishni rivojlantirish va agroxizmatlar bozorini davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash imkoniyatlari.....	550
Shukurov Ilxom Safarboyevich	

Turli mamlakatlarda oliy ta'limni moliyalashtirish yo'llari	557
Umarova Moxigul Maxmayunus qizi	
Dehqonchilikni innovatsion asosda rivojlantirishning xorijiy tajribasi	562
Yuldashev G'iyos Turabekovich	
Tijorat bank xizmat turlarini islomiy bank xizmatlari orqali rivojlantirish istiqbollari	566
Bayjanova Gozzal Sarsengaliyevna	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotini baholash va hisobga olishning uslubiy jihatlarini takomillashtirish	572
Boltayev Abror Sayitmuradovich	
Секреты интересного урока в начальной школе	579
Гараева Олеся Владимировна	
Iqtisodiyotni barqaror rivojlanishda yashil iqtisodiyotning o'rni	582
Ibragimova Gulchehra Toxirovna	
Mahsulot va xizmatlarni raqamli transformatsiyasini amalga oshirish algoritmi	586
Kucharov Abrorjon Sobirjanovich, Bobojonov Azizjon Babaxanovich, Abdurakhmonov Abdumalik Abdurashidovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasining soliq tizimi mamlakatda yashirin iqtisodiyot ulushini qisqartirish vositasi sifatida	593
Nabiyev Feruz Nurmurodovich	
Fundamentals of Innovative Management and its Organizational Control	599
Akramova Aziza Abduvohidovna, Maqsudov Bunyod Abdusamatovich	
Moliyaviy menejment tizimini rivojlantirishda raqamli marketingdan foydalanishning afzalliklari	604
Sobirjonov Sanjar Sobirjonovich	
Оценка экономической эффективности использования фотоэлектрической тепловой установки	608
Жураев Ислom Рахматович, Юлдошев Исроил Абриевич, Жураева Зухра Исламовна	
Ilmiy darajali kadrlar tayyorlash sohasida xalqaro tajriba	614
Fazliddinov Shohruh Shamsiddinovich	
Turizm infratuzilmasi va uning tarkibiy tuzilishi	621
Po'latov Ma'murjon Murodjon o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim xizmatlari bozorining rivojlanishi sabablari	625
Abdukadirova Kamola Azimovna	
Mintaqada turizm sohasini rivojlantirishda xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribalari	629
Isomiddinov Inomjon Qurvonali o'g'li	
Ichki turizmni rivojlantirish bo'yicha infrastruktura holati	636
Dehqonov Burxon Rustamovich	
Soliqqa tortish maqsadida kadastr qiymatlarini aniqlash mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish yo'llari	642
Kamilov Abror Anvarovich	
O'zbekistonda uylarning energiya samaradorligini oshirish	647
Dodiyev Fozil O'tkurovich	
O'zbekistonda talant menejmentni tatbiq etish istiqbollari	653
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida tibbiyot sohasini moliyalashtirish istiqbollari	658
Muxammadiyev Ramz Zoirjon o'g'li	
Bulutli texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda resurs xarajatlarini optimallashtirish: tahlil va boshqarish	663
Saitkamolov Muxammadxo'ja Sobirxo'ja o'g'li, Karabayev Rustam Zafarovich	
Milliy iqtisodiyotni rivojlanishida sug'urta institutlarining tutgan o'rni	673
K. A. Sharipov, D. Jo'rayev	
Tadbirkorlik nazariyasining evolyutsion talqini	678
Aripov Oybek Abdullayevich	

Enhance Export Potential of Private Entrepreneurship and Small Venture.....	683
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi	
Mintaqa barqaror rivojlanishini cheklovchi ekologik omillar tahlili.....	690
Adilova Marg'uba Tursunaliyevna	
Improving the Efficiency of Industrial Enterprise Activities in the Age of Digital Technologies	698
Avloqulova Sadoqat Sobirjon qizi	
A study of green marketing practices in the retail industry – Advantages and disadvantages.....	705
Davronova Zilola Gulomovna	
Tijorat banklarining korporativ xizmatlarini transformatsiyalash jarayonini rivojlantirish.....	709
Farmanova O'g'iloy Aliqul qizi	
Davlat moliyaviy nazorat tizimini rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	715
Maxmudov Azamat Normuradovich	
Xorijiy banklarning moliya injiniringi mahsulotlari va rivojlanish istiqbollari	721
Saipnazarov Sherbek Shaylavbekovich	
O'zbekistonda turizm xizmatlari imkoniyatlari: muammo va yechimlar	727
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Xalikov Saydilla Abdraxmanovich	
Sanoat klasterlarini shakllanishining simulyatsiya modelini yaratish	734
Xakimov Ziyodulla Axmadovich, Axmedova Rayxona Jasurbek qizi	
Hududlarni ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirishning xususiyatlari va ustuvor yo'nalishlari	741
Tolibjon Qazaqov Sharifjon o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda zamonaviy texnika va texnologiyalarning xususiyatlari.....	747
Xusanov Ulugbek Nishanovich	
Biologik aktivlar va qishloq xo'jaligi mahsuloti joriy hisobini tashkil etish bo'yicha xorijiy tajribalar	752
Yusupova Mahfuza Baxtiyor qizi	

ENHANCE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND SMALL VENTURE

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the issue of increasing the export potential of small businesses and private enterprises. The purpose of this study is to clarify strategies that strengthen the capabilities of non-traditional exports as a means of economic diversification. Based on qualitative and quantitative analysis, including through computer evaluation of policy documents, an innovative classification of export growth goals was proposed, enriching discussions on Uzbekistan's regional export strategy. As a result of the analysis, inconsistencies between existing regional priorities and national export goals were identified. Based on the analysis of socio-economic development strategies, practical recommendations were developed for bringing them into line with export goals.

Key words: export enhancement, entrepreneurial support, economic diversification.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik subyektlarining eksport salohiyatini oshirish masalasiga bag'ishlangan. Mazkur tadqiqotning maqsadi iqtisodiyotni diversifikatsiya qilishga ko'maklashish vositasi sifatida noan'anaviy eksport imkoniyatlarini mustahkamlovchi strategiyalarni oydinlashtirishga qaratilgan. Sifat va miqdoriy tahlillar asosida, jumladan, dasturiy hujjatlarni kompyuterda baholash orqali O'zbekistonning mintaqaviy eksport strategiyasi bo'yicha munozaralarni boyitib, eksport o'sish maqsadlarini innovatsion tasniflash taklif etilgan. Tahlil natijasida mavjud mintaqaviy ustuvorliklar va milliy eksportlar maqsadlari o'rtasidagi nomuvofiqliklar aniqlangan. Bu esa ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanish strategiyalarini qayta ko'rib chiqish asosida eksport maqsadlariga muvofiqlashtirish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: eksportni oshirish, tadbirkorlikni qo'llab-quvvatlash, iqtisodiyotni diversifikatsiya qilish.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена вопросу повышения экспортного потенциала малого бизнеса и частных предприятий. Целью данного исследования является разъяснение стратегий, которые укрепляют возможности нетрадиционного экспорта как средства диверсификации экономики. На основе качественного и количественного анализа, в том числе посредством компьютерной оценки программных документов, была предложена инновационная классификация целей роста экспорта, обогатившая дискуссии по региональной экспортной стратегии Узбекистана. В результате анализа были выявлены несоответствия существующих региональных приоритетов национальным экспортным целям. На основе анализа стратегий социально-экономического развития были разработаны практические рекомендации по их приведению в соответствие с экспортными целями.

Ключевые слова: увеличение экспорта, поддержка предпринимательства, диверсификация экономики.

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan's reliance on a narrow range of exports has been a persistent concern within economic circles, accentuated by the strategic reevaluation of national development goals in 2020. This reevaluation pivoted towards fostering sustainable GDP growth through diversification and enhancing the export potential of private entrepreneurship and small businesses, beyond the traditional sectors. This shift reflects a broader intent to leverage untapped economic accelerators, as outlined by prominent Uzbek governmental figures, who emphasize the critical role of investment acceleration, SME development, export support for non-traditional goods, and productivity enhancement in driving economic growth.

Despite recognizing the significance of various growth drivers, this study zeroes in on the external economic dimension, particularly the expansion of non-traditional exports. Preliminary assessments suggest that increasing these exports could significantly contribute to annual GDP growth, underscoring the need for a comprehensive strategy to elevate Uzbekistan's position in global trade markets. Challenges remain, however, including regulatory hurdles and a lack of sustained growth in non-traditional export sectors, which underscores the importance of devising effective strategies for export diversification.

This backdrop sets the stage for our investigation, which seeks to refine the methodology for integrating export development targets into regional strategic planning, thereby enhancing the institutional framework for economic diversification. The study proposes to systematize theoretical approaches to regional strategy formulation, develop a framework for identifying and categorizing export development targets, and offer practical recommendations for regional authorities to effectively align their socio-economic development strategies with national export diversification goals.

Fig 1: The volume of exports of non-resource and non-energy goods of the Republic of Uzbekistan, million USD

The exploration into regional non-resource export strategies, as articulated in policy documents, represents a novel approach to dissecting and enhancing the institutional mechanisms governing foreign economic activity (FEA) within Uzbekistan. Employing modern analytical techniques to scrutinize these documents, this study aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the institutional factors influencing export development, thereby contributing to the broader goal of economic diversification and growth.

In Uzbekistan, the disparity among regions regarding their contributions to non-resource and non-energy exports is notable. Considering the broader opportunities for export, regions such as the Fergana Valley and Tashkent Province have emerged as significant contributors to diversifying the nation's export portfolio. For instance, the Fergana Valley's share of Uzbekistan's non-resource and non-energy exports is markedly higher than its overall export share, indicating a strategic move towards diversification. Similarly, Tashkent Province stands out for its substantial contribution, underscoring the importance of leveraging regional strengths to enhance the country's export potential.

Furthermore, Uzbekistan's border regions hold a unique position in the realm of foreign economic activity, given their geographical proximity to key markets in Central Asia and beyond. These regions have the potential to capitalize on their strategic locations to minimize transportation costs and enhance the competitiveness of Uzbek exports. Yet, historical data suggest that the contribution of these border areas to the national export figure has remained modest, highlighting an underutilized advantage in international trade dynamics.

This article aims to refine the approach to setting developmental targets for non-resource and non-energy exports within regional strategies, recognizing these targets as pivotal for achieving economic diversification through enhanced private entrepreneurship and small business exports. The objectives are to:

1. Systematize theoretical frameworks underscoring the significance of regional strategies as institutional drivers for diversifying non-resource exports.
2. Develop a taxonomy of target indicators for non-resource and non-energy export growth, tailored to the socio-economic contexts of Uzbekistan's diverse regions.
3. Offer actionable recommendations for regional authorities to refine the definition and implementation of approved export development targets, thereby aligning them more closely with national diversification goals.

By focusing on one of the key institutional factors – approved target indicators – this study examines regional non-resource export strategies outlined in Uzbekistan’s policy documents. This analysis is groundbreaking in its use of advanced automated techniques to dissect the textual content of these documents, a method not previously applied in the examination of export strategies within the Uzbek context. The research aims to deliver a comprehensive content analysis of regulatory documents and regional target indicators, thereby contributing to the systematic diversification and development of Uzbekistan’s export sector.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is grounded in an extensive theoretical foundation that combines insights from foreign economic activity literature, emphasizing the strategic role of regions in export diversification, with principles from institutional economics concerning the normative significance of legal frameworks. Furthermore, it incorporates a systemic approach and draws upon both international and local scholarly work examining the multifaceted aspects of regional export dynamics. The synthesis of these perspectives sheds light on the intricacies of developing regional strategies for bolstering non-resource exports, identifying the regulatory environment as a key institutional determinant.

Non-resource Regional Export Strategy: Literature reveals a dichotomy in strategic approaches to enhancing foreign economic activity. One perspective focuses on the strategies of exporting enterprises, which is less prevalent in current literature. The alternative, more dominant view, evaluates the role of governmental bodies, including regional authorities, in fostering export diversification. Despite acknowledgment of the need for diversifying export bases, research consistently points to the volatility faced by exporters of non-resource and non-energy goods, highlighting the necessity for further exploration into stabilizing and enhancing export performance.

Regional Contributions to Export Diversification: Studies, such as those by Gulin et al., underscore the significant disparity among Russian regions in their non-resource export capabilities. Such analyses underscore the critical need to pinpoint regions with untapped export potentials. Researchers advocate for export support programs aimed at broadening the spectrum of non-resource and non-energy goods. Yet, strategic elements within regulatory documents often undergo superficial evaluation, focusing merely on their presence rather than their substantive impact on export development.

The Role of the Regional Regulatory Framework: The consensus among scholars is that legal regulations form a crucial component of the foreign trade ecosystem, acting as vital institutional facilitators for export growth. Research by Mingaleva and others underscores the disparities in regional governance of foreign economic activities, suggesting the necessity for regions to devise bespoke strategies that align with global market demands. This necessitates a thorough examination of regional export strategies concerning non-resource and non-energy sectors.

Furthermore, the typology proposed by Vardomsky et al., categorizing Russian regions based on their foreign economic policies and regulatory depth, provides a nuanced understanding of the legislative landscape. However, this classification system primarily hinges on the existence of regulatory documents, without delving into the strategic priorities emphasized within, particularly regarding non-resource exports.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

This study employs an interdisciplinary approach to evaluate Uzbekistan’s legislative framework geared towards enhancing the export potential of private entrepreneurship and small businesses. It combines techniques from both the natural and social sciences for the automated analysis of texts, incorporating content analysis elements, and adapts legal methodologies for scrutinizing normative documents. This approach aligns with the methodologies established by scholars such as Mannheim and Averyanov, focusing on both qualitative and quantitative dimensions of document analysis, characterized by objectivity and procedural rigor.

In legal scholarship, there’s a rich tradition of textual analysis, initially centered on qualitative methods. This tradition underscores the linguistic characteristics of legal texts as systems of signs, facilitating a deeper comprehension of the documents. The integration of automated systems for analyzing normative texts represents a shift towards the “informational approach to law,” enhancing the efficiency and breadth of textual analysis through the application of computational linguistics and information technologies.

This study seeks to extend the application of text analysis methods to the investigation of foreign economic activity, emphasizing the use of automated content analysis for examining normative documents. This includes the assessment of strategic elements within regulatory frameworks that support non-resource and non-energy exports, utilizing frequency content analysis to highlight key policy partners and strategic priorities.

The methodology comprises several steps:

1. **Defining the Study's Purpose and Hypotheses:** The aim is to develop a classification of target indicators for the enhancement of non-resource and non-energy exports in Uzbekistan, assess their alignment with federal legislation, and offer recommendations for policy refinement. Two hypotheses guide this analysis: first, that regions with significant development potential prioritize non-resource export strategies before the enactment of corresponding federal laws; second, that some regional target indicators might not fully align with federal guidelines.
2. **Document Selection:** The empirical base is constructed from regional documents featuring themes of non-resource exports, categorized into specific strategies and broader socio-economic development plans. The focus is on socio-economic development strategies across various regions, reflecting the prioritization of non-resource export development.
3. **Development of a Conceptual Model:** A set of key concepts and keywords related to non-resource and non-energy exports is identified to structure the analysis and ensure the relevance of selected documents.
4. **Identification of Assessment Units:** The analysis utilizes the proportion of keywords to the total word count in each document, expressing this ratio as a measure of relevance. This method facilitates the comparison of documents of varying lengths and focuses on how keywords represent the document's overall content.

By leveraging these methodologies, the study endeavors to provide a nuanced understanding of Uzbekistan's legislative and strategic framework for export diversification, aiming to support the growth of private entrepreneurship and small businesses in the global market. Начало формы

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The empirical investigation conducted in this study adhered to a structured approach, thoroughly examining each hypothesis through a series of methodical analyses. The findings for each hypothesis are detailed below.

- **Hypothesis I:** The initial phase aimed to uncover the degree to which non-resource and non-energy export priorities were reflected and had evolved across different regions prior to the federal acknowledgment of these priorities in the May Decree of 2018. Utilizing the "Istio" software for keyword frequency analysis, the investigation scrutinized strategic documents from the period of 2017-2020. This analysis sought to identify regions that had proactively adopted non-resource and non-energy export priorities. The keyword focus was on "non-energy" in conjunction with "non-resource" and/or "export," including all variations of these terms.

The analysis revealed that, out of the NWFD regions examined, nine featured the designated keywords in their strategic documents, suggesting an awareness of non-resource and non-energy export development priorities. However, strategies from the Kaliningrad and Murmansk regions did not explicitly mention these keywords, though they did acknowledge the significance of export orientation in general.

Contrary to the initial hypothesis, no NWFD region had formally adopted non-resource and non-energy export priorities in their strategic documents before such priorities were nationally recognized in 2018. The incorporation of these priorities into regional strategies predominantly occurred in 2019, a year following their federal endorsement, with three regions (Vologda, Leningrad, and Pskov) integrating these priorities into their strategies by 2020.

- **Hypothesis II:** The verification of this hypothesis involved constructing a text corpus from regional strategies that addressed non-resource and non-energy exports, totaling 181 words. The corpus underwent lemmatization, simplifying each word to its base form using the "MyStem" software, a common practice among Russian researchers for text analysis. Subsequent to this processing, non-essential elements such as conjunctions, prepositions, and punctuation were removed, allowing for a clearer focus on relevant terms.

A word cloud generated from the refined corpus visually highlighted the frequency of specific phrases and words related to non-resource and non-energy exports. This visualization technique underscored the thematic emphasis within the strategies, offering insights into how regions articulate and prioritize these export domains.

- **Discussion:** The study's findings indicate a nuanced landscape of regional strategic alignment with federal export priorities in Uzbekistan. While there is a clear recognition of the importance of diversifying exports beyond traditional resources and energies, the timing and explicitness of this recognition vary across regions. The absence of explicit keywords in certain regional strategies does not necessarily imply a lack of export orientation; rather, it may reflect differences in strategic focus or terminology.

The adaptation of non-resource and non-energy export priorities appears to be reactive rather than proactive, with regions aligning their strategies with federal directives post-2018. This lag in adoption suggests opportunities for enhancing regional strategic responsiveness and for fostering a more integrated approach to national export diversification efforts.

This research underscores the potential of automated text analysis as a tool for assessing policy alignment and for identifying thematic emphases within legal and strategic documents. By leveraging technology to parse and analyze the content of regional strategies, policymakers and researchers can gain valuable insights into the alignment and focus of economic development efforts across different administrative levels.

Fig. 2: Word cloud of provisions for non-resource and non-energy exports, contained in the strategies of socio-economic development of the regions in the NWFĐ*

Analysis of the Uzbekistan Regions' Strategies for Enhancing Non-Resource and Non-Energy Small Business Exports

In the context of Uzbekistan's efforts to bolster the export potential of private entrepreneurship and small businesses in non-resource and non-energy sectors, an analytical examination of current regional strategies provides insightful revelations. This analysis, centered on keyword frequencies and thematic emphases within these strategies, uncovers significant variations and the prevalence of specific export-related goals.

Key Findings:

- 1. Prevalent Themes:** The analysis identified recurrent themes, with "export of non-resource and non-energy goods" emerging as the most frequently mentioned phrase. This focus underscores a nationwide push towards diversifying the export base beyond traditional sectors.
- 2. Quantitative Goals:** References to financial benchmarks, such as "billion US dollars" and "million US dollars," highlight the economic aspirations tied to these export initiatives. The inclusion of specific financial targets suggests a measurable approach to tracking progress in enhancing export capabilities.
- 3. Varied Formulations:** The diversity in the expression of goals and indicators across regions points to a tailored approach to export development. This diversity reflects the unique economic landscapes and potential of each region, necessitating customized strategies for export enhancement.

Classification and Compliance:

A proposed classification system for regional target indicators categorizes these based on their formalization level and alignment with national directives. Notably, none of the strategies explicitly match the latest fed-

eral benchmarks for 2020, indicating a gap between regional planning and national objectives. This misalignment raises concerns about the coherence of Uzbekistan's strategy to amplify non-resource and non-energy exports on a national scale.

Discussion:

The disparities in goal formalization and compliance with federal guidelines underscore the need for a more harmonized approach across Uzbekistan's regions. While the ambition to enhance non-resource and non-energy exports is evident, the effectiveness of these efforts may be compromised by inconsistencies in strategic planning and execution.

Recommendations for Regional Authorities:

To address these challenges and capitalize on the evident progress in some regions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Strategic Revision and Alignment:** Regions lacking explicit provisions for non-resource and non-energy export enhancement in their strategies should undertake revisions to incorporate specific, measurable targets that align with national objectives. This alignment is crucial for creating a unified front in boosting Uzbekistan's export diversity.
2. **Emphasizing Quantifiable Targets:** Adopting clear financial benchmarks and timelines can significantly enhance strategy effectiveness. These targets not only facilitate progress monitoring but also enable the identification of successful initiatives that can be scaled or adapted across regions.
3. **Clarification and Specification:** Regions should aim to clarify and specify their export development targets to avoid ambiguities that may hinder implementation. Clear, detailed goals will support more focused efforts and resource allocation towards achieving significant export growth.

By integrating these recommendations into their strategic planning, Uzbekistan's regions can significantly contribute to the national goal of diversifying exports. Such efforts will not only enhance the economic resilience of private entrepreneurship and small businesses but also position Uzbekistan more prominently on the global export map.

CONCLUSION

The thorough examination of Uzbekistan's strategic approach to bolstering non-resource and non-energy exports from private entrepreneurship and small businesses has underscored the critical role of regional strategies in national economic diversification efforts. This study, covering strategies from 2017 to early 2021, applied both qualitative and quantitative content analysis to over 35 versions of socio-economic development strategies, illuminating the theoretical and practical frameworks guiding Uzbekistan's export enhancement initiatives.

Key Insights:

1. **Strategic Diversity:** The study reveals significant diversity in how regions articulate and prioritize non-resource and non-energy exports. This diversity reflects both the varying economic contexts across Uzbekistan and the evolving nature of national economic priorities.
2. **Theoretical Contributions:** By developing a nuanced classification of non-resource and non-energy export targets, the research contributes to the broader theoretical understanding of regional export strategies. This classification helps delineate the best practices for formulating export priorities and target indicators within regional regulatory frameworks.
3. **Novelty and Evolution:** The analysis traces the evolution of non-resource and non-energy export priorities within regional strategies, identifying key terms and constructs that encapsulate these priorities. Furthermore, it underscores the necessity for regional strategies to adapt to the changing federal system of key performance indicators for export development.
4. **Practical Implications:** Recommendations for Uzbekistan's regional authorities highlight the importance of aligning socio-economic development strategies with updated national targets for non-resource export development. Such alignment is crucial for achieving the broader goal of diversifying Uzbekistan's export base and enhancing the economic potential of private entrepreneurship and small businesses.

Future Studies:

Building on the findings of this study, future research should focus on the economic and statistical evaluation of non-resource and non-energy exports' development impact. This includes exploring additional document types and effective mechanisms to support these exports at the regional level. A comprehensive approach, combining policy analysis with economic data, will provide deeper insights into the efficacy of strategies designed to enhance Uzbekistan's position in the global market.

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